

STRENGTH ANALYSIS OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH A CIRCULAR CUTOUT

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ABSTRACT

Owing to the great advantages of fiber reinforced composite laminates, including the light weight, corrosion resistance, high specific strength and stiffness, etc., the application of composite laminates in engineering structures has been rapidly increasing during the last few decades. In this paper, the strength analysis of carbon fiber reinforced composite laminate with big cutout under unidirectional tension is studied by simulation and experiment. Considering composite laminates with different layups and different circle cutouts, the ultimate strength and failure mode for each laminate are obtained by finite element method. Experiments under unidirectional tension are carried out by the strain gauge measurement and 3D Digital Image Correlation (DIC) method. According to the simulation, four layup sequences and different sizes of cutouts in composite laminates were tested separately. Results show that the failure mode of fiber reinforced composite laminate with big cutout under unidirectional tension is a typical brittle fracture. The crack onset is happened around the high stress concentration area, and the failure mode and crack propagation strongly depend on the ply sequences and the cutout size.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to high specific strength and stiffness as well as flexibility in designing the structural performance, fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) laminated composites have been widely used in many structural applications such as aerospace structures, sports, automotive structures and marine as well as modern bridge decks and buildings. As a heterogeneous anisotropic material, the failure process of composite laminate shows very complicated behavior. In order to meet manufactural and functional requirements, it is unavoidable to have cutouts on primary composite structures. However, it makes the failure criterions face new challenges due to the more complicated failure modes of composite laminates with big cutouts, and there are no acceptable theoretical results to be used.

In this paper, the strength analysis of carbon fiber reinforced composite laminate with a circular cutout under unidirectional tension will be studied by numerical analysis and experimental tests to figure out the failure behaviors.

2 SIMULATION ANALYSIS

In this section, composite laminate with a central circular cutout was considered, and the influences of stacking sequences and opening dimension to the initial load and failure mode were studied by simulation modeling. By using the ABAQUS commercial software, the simulation model applied Hashin criterion to evaluate the initial failure of the laminates with a central circular cutout under the unidirectional tension loading, and the progressive failure process with the stiffness degradation model would be simulated to obtain the ultimate load and failure mode of each laminate. Furthermore, the different layups of laminates included [0]8 unidirectional laminate, [0/90]2s cross-ply, [± 45]2s cross-ply and [0/90/ ± 45]2s quasi isotropic laminates, and the different dimensions of circular cutouts ($\Phi 60$ mm, $\Phi 80$ mm and $\Phi 100$ mm) were taken account of.

3 EXPERIMENT TESTING

According to the numerical models, experiments under unidirectional tension are carried out by the strain gauge measurement and 3D Digital Image Correlation (DIC) method. According to the simulation, four layup sequences and different sizes of cutouts in composite laminates were tested separately. Through the strain gauge measurement and DIC testing, the stress concentrations and the failure modes of composite laminates with big cutouts were obtained. The figure 1 shows the failure modes of laminate specimens with different stacking sequences.

Fig.1 (a) [0]8 laminate; (b) [0/90]2s laminate; (c) [0/90/±45]2s laminate; (d) [±45]2s laminate

9 CONCLUSIONS

The simulation and experimental results show that the failure mode of fiber reinforced composite laminate with big cutout under unidirectional tension is a typical brittle fracture process, but the simulation exhibits a similarity of ductile fracture behavior. Simulation results predict the crack onset happens to the high stress concentration area. But owing to the big cutout, the failure can be caused by the stress concentration and local buckling during the unidirectional tension process. The stress concentration influences the initial failure happens, and the local buckling and the progressive failure process are sometimes occurring and developing simultaneously. It makes the failure mode and crack propagation become very complicated and strongly depend on the ply sequences and the cutout's dimension. Therefore, comparing to the others, [±45]2s cross-ply laminate with big cutout has the lowest ultimate load for its serious delamination failure mode. The bigger size of cutout is, the lower of ultimate load has. After comparison of the experimental and numerical results, it is concluded that the numerical simulation for strength analysis of composite laminate should be improved by further developed criterions.

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